

ISic3020

I.Sicily inscription 3020

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication (?)

Material

limestone

Object

rock

face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2013.10.02 of lower frag only

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Buscemi

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 50162

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332330

1. ἐπὶ
2. ἀμφιπό-
3. λου ἐν Συ-
4. [ρακο]ύσαις [— —]
5. [— — —]ΠΟ [— — —]
6. ²versus 6-11 non lecti sunt²
7. ΠΟ [— — — — —]
8. ΓΕΝ [— — — — —]
9. [Ρ]ουφίλ [λα(?)]
10. Φαυστια [νός(?)]
11. ν Ἄρτέ [μων(?)]
12. ΙΙΧΡΜΝ [— — —]
- 13.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645377

PHI 332330

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 42.0831

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 459-460 no.6

Manganaro, G. 1992. Iscrizioni "rupestri" di Sicilia. In Gasperini, L.(eds.), *Rupes loquentes: atti del convegno internazionale di studio sulle iscrizioni rupestri di età romana in Italia. Roma - Bomarzo 13-15.X.1989*. Rome. pp. 447-501. At 464 no.7

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